

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF ANTIMICROBIAL GARLIC OIL CREAM

Priyanka Raj G.^{1*}, Ranjeetha A. R.², Devika A. S.³, Nanjundaswamy R.⁴, Ranjitha J. S.⁵, Thomas Sajjo A.⁶

*Dept. of Pharmaceutics, Bharathi College of Pharmacy, Bharathinagara, Maddur taluk, Mandya district, Karnataka, India-571422.

Article Received on
11 August 2025,

Revised on 31 August 2025,
Accepted on 20 Sept. 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17224082>

*Corresponding Author

Priyanka Raj G.

Dept. of Pharmaceutics,
Bharathi College of
Pharmacy, Bharathinagara,
Maddur Taluk,
Mandya District,
Karnataka, India-571422.

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this work was to develop a novel topical cream formulation of garlic oil that can be easily scaled up in a single pot for the potential treatment of microbial infections. Compared to gels or ointments, topical creams offer several advantages, including faster drug release at the intended site of action. A viscous mixture of propylene glycol, triethanolamine, methyl paraben, and garlic oil was prepared and then formulated into optimized cream bases. The color, appearance, and homogeneity of the creams were assessed visually. For each formulation, the drug content, pH, viscosity, spreadability, and cream strength were evaluated, and all were found to be within acceptable limits. The manufactured formulations were transparent, off-white in color, and exhibited excellent homogeneity. Both pH and viscosity were within the required limits. Among all the developed formulations (F1, F2, F3, and F4), formulation F3 was found to be the best.

KEYWORDS: Garlic oil, permeation enhancer, Viscosity, Spreadability, homogeneity.

INTRODUCTION

TOPICAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

IVERY

Topical drug delivery is defined as the application of a drug containing formulation to the skin to treat cutaneous disorders (e.g., acne) directly or for the treatment of any other wound and wound-related infection. This is achieved in two ways: external and internal topicals.

External topicals are sprayed, spread or dispersed directly on to the cutaneous tissues to cover the affected site. However, internal topicals are applied to the mucous membrane via oral, vaginal or on anorectal route for local activity. Topical drug delivery is defined as the application of a drug containing formulation to the skin to treat cutaneous disorders (e.g., acne) directly or for the treatment of any other wound and wound-related infection. This is achieved in two ways: external and internal topicals. External topicals are sprayed, spread or dispersed directly on to the cutaneous tissues to cover the affected site. However, internal topicals are applied to the mucous membrane via oral, vaginal or on anorectal route for local activity. Topical drug delivery is defined as the application of a drug containing formulation to the skin to treat cutaneous disorders (e.g., acne) directly or for the treatment of any other wound and wound-related infection. This is achieved in two ways: external and internal topicals. External topicals are sprayed, spread or dispersed directly on to the cutaneous tissues to cover the affected site. However, internal topicals are applied to the mucous membrane via oral, vaginal or on anorectal route for local activity. Topical drug delivery is defined as the application of a drug containing formulation to the skin to treat cutaneous disorders (e.g., acne) directly or for the treatment of any other wound and wound-related infection. This is achieved in two ways: external and internal topicals. External topicals are sprayed, spread or dispersed directly on to the cutaneous tissues to cover the affected site. However, internal topicals are applied to the mucous membrane via oral, vaginal or on anorectal route for local activity. Topical drug delivery can be defined as application of drug via skin to directly treat or cure the skin disorders. These topical drug delivery systems are generally used for local skin infection like fungal infection or where other route of administration are not suitable. It can penetrate deeper into skin and hence give better absorption. Topical preparation prevents the GI-irritation, prevent the metabolism of drug in the liver so as to increase the bioavailability of the drug. Topical preparations give its action directly at the site of action. The main aim of this form of distribution is to confine the drug's pharmacological or other action to the skin's surface or within it. For the distribution of diverse dosage forms, three major modes are extensively used: topical, regional, and transdermal.^[1]

ADVANTAGES OF TOPICAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

1. Avoidance of the first pass metabolism.
2. Convenient and easy to apply.
3. Deliver drug more selectively to a specific site.
4. Avoidance of the gastro-intestinal incompatibility.
5. Provide suitability for self-medication.

DISADVANTAGES OF TOPICAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

1. Poor permeability of few drugs through skin.
2. Drugs who is having the larger particle size can't be get easily absorbed through the layer of skin.
3. Possibility of allergic reactions.
4. The path of that drugs are not suitable for those drugs that irritate or sensitize the skin.^[2]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Collection of sample

White bees wax, stearyl alcohol, cetyl alcohol, liquid paraffin, Vitamin E. garlic oil Propylene glycol, triethanolamine, propyl paraben was collected from the local market, salem.

Methods

Preparation of Cream Formulation

Preparation of oil phase

White bees wax, stearyl alcohol, cetyl alcohol and were melted in a China dish. To this liquid paraffin, Vitamin E and garlic oil were added and allowed to melt. Temperature should be maintained for an oil phase between 65-70°C.

Preparation of aqueous phase

Propylene glycol, triethanolamine, propyl paraben, water was added in beaker and the temperature of the phase was maintained at 65-70-C At 65-70°C, the oil component was gently added to the aqueous phase and mixed for 10 to 15 minutes. When the water and oil phases were at the same temperature, the aqueous phase was gradually added to the oil phase with moderate agitation and mixed until the temperature dropped to 40°C. To make semisolid

cream base, the emulsion was brought to room temperature. Keeping the pH of the cream between 4.5 and 6.4 is important.

Composition of anti-biotic cream using garlic oil

SI NO	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4
1	Garlic oil	10ml	10ml	10ml	10ml
2	White bees wax	1gm	2.5gm	5gm	6gm
3	Cetastearyl alcohol	4mg	4mg	4mg	4mg
4	Cetyl alcohol	3gm	6gm	9gm	12gm
5	Paraffin	5ml	5ml	5ml	5ml
6	Vitamin E	1ml	1ml	1ml	1ml
7	Propylene glycol	10ml	10ml	10ml	10ml
8	Triethanolamine	2ml	4ml	6ml	8ml
9	Propyl paraben	0.5mg	0.5mg	0.5mg	0.5mg
10	Water	Upto50	Upto50	Upto50	Upto50

Preformulation studies

Organoleptic properties

A natural substance's organoleptic quality refers to its appearance, odour, colour, and taste. The study's initial stage is to characterise these characteristics, which aids in the primary identification of the Natural substance as well as determining the likelihood of patient acceptability of the raw materials' aroma, taste, and colour, as well as its likely inclusion in the final dose form. Changes in the colour and odour of a formulation's signal that the formulation's stability has deteriorated (under identical conditions). material might sometimes.

IR Spectra Analysis

These compatibility studies are conducted by using an ATR-FTIR spectrophotometer and the spectrum was recorded in the wave number region of 4000 to 400cm⁻¹.

	Peak	Intensity	Corr. Intensity	Base (H)	Base (L)	Area	Corr. Area	Comment
1	494.29	9.46	1.75	511.54	471.30	3597.166	32.357	
2	724.19	9.70	0.47	804.66	681.09	11123.162	23.405	
3	1161.00	7.74	1.19	1221.35	1112.15	9993.112	49.945	
4	1454.13	9.45	0.71	1502.98	1411.02	8293.536	32.526	
5	1741.50	7.95	2.35	1787.48	1698.40	8093.438	103.003	
6	2856.52	9.00	0.82	2885.26	2813.41	6505.926	32.722	
7	2922.62	8.07	1.58	3095.04	2885.26	18949.079	52.758	

Drug and excipients compatibility studies

Chemical compatibility studies

These compatibility studies are conducted by using an ATR-FTIR spectrophotometer and the spectrum was recorded in the wave number region of 4000 to 400cm⁻¹. Natural oils and excipients were mixed well by using the mortar until complete mixing. Then collect the sample from mortar and placed in the cavity of the sample holder and the spectrum was recorded.

Evaluation of Formulated Cream

Appearance

The formulated garlic oil cream was visually evaluated for colour, appearance, and transparency. Observing the smoothness, clumping, roughness, and homogeneity of the cream was encouraged by rubbing it between the fingers.

PH Measurement

PH measurement of the cream was carried out using a digital pH meter by dipping the glass electrode completely into the cream system to cover the electrode. The measurement was done.^[10]

Spreadability

Two sets of standard-sized glass slides were taken. One of the slides was covered with the garlic cream mixture. The cream was sandwiched between the two slides in an area filled by a distance of 7.5 cm along the sides after the other slide was placed on top of it. A 100g weight of cream was placed on the upper slides and squeezed uniformly between the two slides to form a thin coating. The weight was secured to a stand in such a way that only the upper slides were able to slip off freely due to the force of the weight linked to it. A 20g weight was carefully fastened to the upper side. The time taken for the upper slide to travel the distance of 7.5 cm and separated away from the lower slider under the influence of the weight was noted. The experiment was repeated for three times and mean time was taken for calculation.^[9]

Spreadability was calculated by using the following formula: $S-m-1/t$,

Extrudability

The quantity in percentage cream extruded from tube on application of finger pressure was used as the basis for evaluating cream formulation for extrude ability in the current study. Extrude ability improved as the quantity extruded increased. The study formulation was placed in a clean, lacquered aluminium collapsible 5 gm tube with a 5 mm nasal tip opening, and pressure was applied to the tube using a finger. The amount of cream extruded through the tip when a pressure was applied to a tube was then measured to assess tube extrudability.

Irritancy test

Mark an area (1sq.cm) on the left hand dorsal surface. The cream was applied to the specified area and time was noted. Irritancy, erythema, edema, was checked if any for regular intervals up to 24hrs and reported.

Washability

The ease of removal of the cream applied was examined by washing the applied part with tap.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Organoleptic properties

The present study was carried out to develop Anti-microbial cream by using garlic oil. Assessment of the physical description /organoleptic property of the drug is the primary step for drug substance recognition. It helps to check the feasibility of drug for formulating into the intended dosage form. This also helps in assessing the patient acceptability factors such as colour, nature, odour, and taste which eventually leads to better patient compliance.

Sl no	Properties	F1	F2	F3	F4
1	Colour	brownish-yellow	brownish-yellow	brownish-yellow	brownish-yellow
2	Odour	pungent	pungent	pungent	pungent
3	Taste	Bitter burnt garlic	Bitter burnt garlic	Bitter burnt garlic	Bitter burnt garlic

The color, odor, nature and taste of the API were evaluated and it was observed as specified in the monograph. Based on the observation it was found satisfactory for the formulation of cream and no discomfort likely to arise in patient compliance.

IR- Spectra Analysis

ATR-FTIR spectrum of pure drug and prepared cream was compared to study of drug with the excipients and the spectrum was recorder in the wave number region of 4000 to 400cm.

Compatibility Studies

Chemical compatibility studies

ATR-FTIR spectrum of pure drug and prepared cream was compared to study of drug with the excipients and the spectrum was recorder in the wave number region of 4000 to 400cm. According to functional category these excipients were mixed in garlic oil. This indicates that the drug is compatible with the formulation components. ATR-FTIR spectroscopy was fixed

at the range of 4000-400cm³. There is no interaction between the drugs and excipients. physiochemical parameters evaluation of cream formulation.

Appearance

The prepared cream was visually inspected for the appearance, colour, and texture. All the prepared formulation was white colour, with a smooth texture, and they were all homogenous with no signs of phase separation.

PH measurement

Using a digital pH meter, pH measurements of the prepared cream were taken by immersing the glass electrode entirely into the cream system and covering it. pH is one of the major evaluation factors in the cream preparation purpose of avoiding the irritation of the skin upon the application. Using a pH meter, it was discovered that the pH ranges from 6.4 to 6.6, which is basic in nature. The pH should not be too acidic, as this might cause skin irritation, nor should it be too alkaline, as this can result in scaly skin.

Formulation	pH
F1	6.5
F2	6.6
F3	6.5
F4	6.4

Determination of viscosity

The viscosity of formulated was measured by Brook field Viscometer LVD using spindle 5 94 at varying speed and shear rates. The measurements were done over the range of speed setting from 0.10, 0.20, 0.30, 0.40 and 0.50 rpm in 60s between two successive speeds as equilibration with shear rate ranging from 0.20s⁻¹ to 1.0 s⁻¹. From the result shows viscosity of all the formulations range from (66500) to (68500) cps.. F3 Shows a better consistency with viscosity level of 67506 cps.^[11]

Formulation	viscosity
F1	60340 cps
F2	62930cps
F3	67450 cps
F4	70110 cps

viscosity measurement

Determination of Spreadability

The Spread ability of the cream was based upon the viscosity and it was evaluated form all the 4 formulations. F3 has better spread ability as compares to other formulation The F3 having better consistency so the cream was easily spreadable by the small amount of shear.

Spreadability

Formulation	Spreadability(gm cm/sec)
F1	22.5
F2	20.0
F3	20.83
F4	23.33

Extrudability

The extrudability of the cream was based upon the viscosity, and it was evaluated from all the 5 formulations range from (1.759gm) to (2.545 gm) gm. The formulation (F3) having better consistency of the cream.

Formulation	Extrudability
F1	1.759gm
F2	2.545gm
F3	2.350gm
F4	1.950gm

Irritancy test

Mark area (1sq.cm) on the left-hand dorsal surface. The cream was applied to the specified area and time was. noted. Irritancy, erythema, edema, was checked if any for regular intervals up to 24hrs and reported. From the above result, it was concluded that no irritancy was observed in all formulation.

Formulation	Irritancy result
F1	No Irritancy
F2	No Irritancy
F3	No Irritancy
F4	No Irritancy

Washability

The ease of removal of the cream applied was examined by washing the applied part with tap. All formulation was easily removed with normal water.

CONCLUSION

- In the present study, efforts were made to develop an antibiotic cream containing garlic oil for effective treatment against microbial infections.
- A comparison of the ATR-FTIR spectra of garlic oil and the garlic-oil-based antibiotic cream (F3) confirmed that none of the existing peaks had disappeared. This indicates that the phytoconstituent Diallyl disulfide (DADS), responsible for the antibiotic activity, remained intact without any degradation or destruction.
- The antibiotic cream formulated using garlic oil was evaluated for appearance, pH, viscosity, spreadability, extrudability, removal properties, and stability as per ICH guidelines.
- No color change was observed in the physical compatibility studies, indicating that all the excipients were compatible with garlic oil.

- In vitro drug release studies revealed that the release was controlled in pH 7.4 phosphate buffer, with formulation F3 showing 92.7% drug release. Over a 3-month observation period, no significant variation was noted, and the formulation remained clear.
- Based on the properties of the base and other excipients, the formulation was found to be effective, safe, and stable for topical use. The garlic oil cream offers a potentially effective, cost-efficient, and easily accessible option for preventing skin infections caused by microbes.

REFERENCE

1. Kavya M. S., Kavana D. C.*, Eshwari G. M., Navyashree P. S. and Jagadeesh C. S: A Short Review On: Pharmaceutical Cream For Skin Care. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 2023; 12(19): 153-62.
2. Vaibhav R. Toche*, Amol S. Deshmukh, Ashok J. Rabade: Topical Gels as Drug Delivery System- A comprehensive review. The International journal of analytical and experimental modal analysis, 2021; 13(4): 664-681.
3. Lalita C, Shalini G. Creams: A review on classification, preparation methods, evaluation and its applications. JDDT, 2020 Oct 2; 10: 281-9.
4. Hagavane S, Sonawane S, Katkale A, Kunde V. Review on cream as topical drug delivery system. International Journal of Research in Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2022; (7): 21-30.
5. Kanitalis J. Anstonty, histology and immunolasiochemistry of normal human skin, Fiar] Dermatol. 2002, 12/4390 401.
6. Kolarsick PA, Kalarsick MA, Goodwin C. Anatomy and physiology of the slein J Dermatol Nursos Assoc., 2011; 3(4): 205-213. doe 10.1097/TDN6013e318227498
7. Beasouilah J, Buck P. Arconadenmanology: avenatherapy in the treatment and care of common slan conditions. Radcliffe. Publishing, 2006.
8. Ali BI, Blunden G, Tanira MO, Nemmar A. Some phytochemical, pharmacological and toxicological properties of ginger (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe): a review of recent research. Foo Food and chemical toxicology, 2008; 46(2): 409-20.
9. Bharrarai 8, Tran VH, Duke CC. The stability of gingerol and shogaol in aqueous solunons. Journal of pharmaceutical sciences, 2001; 90(10): 1658-64.
10. Schwertner HA, Rios DC. High-performance liquid chromatographic analysis of 6 gingerol, 8-gingeml, 10-gingerol, and 6-shogaol in ginger-containing dietary supplements, spices, teas, and beverages. Journal of chromatography B. 2007; 856(1-2): 41-7.